

Myths in psychology: Psychological misconceptions among Spanish psychology students

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Myths in Psychology are beliefs that are widely spread and inconsistent with the empirical evidence available within this field of knowledge. They are characterized by being relatively stable, resistant to change, and prevalent both among the non-academic population and among students and professionals within this discipline. The aim of this study was to analyse the prevalence of these myths among Spanish psychology students and the influence of three variables: the type of university, face-to-face (UAM) and online (UNED), the academic year in which participants were enrolled and familiarity with scientific dissemination. Results show that participants from the face-to-face university, enrolled in higher academic years and that reports familiarity with scientific dissemination believe less in myths than those from the online university, enrolled in lower years and that report no familiarity with scientific dissemination.

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Psychological misconceptions among Spanish psychology students

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Abstract

20 Myths in Psychology are beliefs that are widely spread and inconsistent with the empirical evidence
21 available within this field of knowledge. They are characterized by being relatively stable, resistant
22 to change, and prevalent both among the non-academic population and among students and
23 professionals within this discipline. The aim of this study was to analyse the prevalence of these
24 myths among Spanish psychology students and the influence of three variables: the type of
25 university, face-to-face (UAM) and online (UNED), the academic year in which participants were
26 enrolled and familiarity with scientific dissemination. Results show that participants from the face-
27 to-face university, enrolled in higher academic years and that reports familiarity with scientific
28 dissemination believe less in myths than those from the online university, enrolled in lower years
29 and that report no familiarity with scientific dissemination.

30 **Keywords:** myths in psychology, higher education, academic year, scientific
31 dissemination.

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32 Myths in Psychology are defined as beliefs about human behavior that are inconsistent with
33 the available scientific evidence but that exhibit great social support (Lilienfeld et al., 2010;
34 Stanovich, 1992). Contrary to certain expectations, these misconceptions are not only
35 believed by people outside of Psychology, but also prevail among professionals within this
36 discipline (Fasce & Adrián-Ventura, 2020; Furnham & Hughes, 2014; Galassi & Gersh,
37 1993; Hooper, 2006; Houben et al., 2019; Lilienfeld et al., 2013; Torres, Boccacini &
38 Miller 2006). Although some studies show that university studies reduce the belief in myths
39 (Bensley, Lilienfeld & Powell, 2014; Hughes et al., 2015; Sibicky, Klein & Embrescia,
40 2020), it has also been shown that having university studies does not eliminate the belief in
41 myths nor are these beliefs fully replaced with explanations from scientific psychology
42 (Hughes et al., 2015; Lyddy & Hughes, 2012; Root & Stanley, 2017). On many occasions,
43 students who begin their studies in Psychology have imprecise and contradictory
44 information about human behavior (Hughes, Lyddy & Lambe, 2013). The resistance to
45 change that characterizes these ideas is due to a history of intermittent and repeated
46 exposure to these false facts through socializing agents such as the media, family or peers
47 (Furnham & Hughes, 2014; Kowalski & Taylor, 2004). This favors the creation of a
48 confirmation bias when presented with new information (Furnham & Hughes, 2014;
49 Kowalski & Taylor, 2004). In this way, most popular knowledge is not disproven and
50 cannot be replaced by more adjusted beliefs (Lilienfeld et al., 2010; Stanovich, 1992),
51 which leads, in many cases, to its consequences reaching the professional practice of those
52 students who complete this stage of education (Furnham & Hughes, 2014).

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53 Believing that some erroneous statements in psychology are true is not a trivial
54 phenomenon and can lead to serious negative effects, such as the implementation of
55 harmful practices in educational or clinical areas, for example (Lilienfeld et al., 2010). The
56 belief in myths also hinders the development of learning content related to the discipline
57 and critical thinking within and outside of Psychology (Lilienfeld et al., 2010). It can even
58 legitimize existing inequalities in society, such as the differences between men and women,
59 the stigma towards people with mental health problems, or the consequences that derive
60 from the naturalistic fallacy (i.e., where everything natural is desirable and, therefore,
61 unchangeable) (Lester, Strunk & Hoover, 2020; Lilienfeld et al., 2010).

62 The study of misconceptions in Psychology began in the second decade of the 20th century
63 (e.g., Nixon, 1925, see also Tupper & Williams, 1986). Since then, numerous studies have
64 been carried out, either by reviewing myths in different general areas of Psychology (e.g.,
65 Lilienfeld et al., 2010) or by focusing on more specific aspects of the discipline, such as
66 myths about schizophrenia (Furnham & Bower, 1992), ontological development and
67 neuropsychology (Furnham, 2018; Furnham & Grover, 2019), intelligence (Warne, Astle &
68 Hill, 2018) or behavior analysis (Lamal, 1995). However, the study of myths is not limited
69 to behavioral science. The prevalence of myths has been studied in fields such as Education
70 (Ferrero, Garaizar & Vadillo, 2016), Medicine (Kaufman et al., 2013) or public health
71 policies (Viehbeck, Petticrew & Cummins, 2015), as well as in science as a knowledge
72 system (McComas, 1996), and the practical consequences that they entail, such as those
73 caused by the myths of mathematics in their students (Powell & Nelson, 2021).

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Relevant factors in the belief in myths in Psychology

76 Several studies show that the progression of the students in psychology education.
77 measured with variables such as the academic year or the course credits earned, is related to
78 the prevalence of myths in the field of Psychology. For example, a positive relationship has
79 been found between academic history and the recognition of myths as such, in addition to a
80 greater predisposition to abandon this type of beliefs (Bensley, Lilienfeld & Powell, 2014;
81 Gardner & Brown, 2013; Gardner & Dalsing, 1986; Gaze, 2014). This effect has been
82 found in pre-post (e.g., Taylor & Kowalsky, 2004, 2009), cross-sectional (e.g., Amsel,
83 Baird, & Ashley, 2011; Gardner & Dalsing, 1986) and longitudinal design (McCarthy &
84 Frantz, 2016).

85 Some studies suggest that psychology students are better at recognizing the myths in this
86 discipline than the general population or students from other university degrees (Bensley,
87 Lilienfeld & Powell, 2014; Furnham & Hughes, 2014; Gardner & Dalsing, 1986; Hughes et
88 al., 2015; Sibicky, Klein & Embrescia, 2020). Reaching a higher academic year could
89 indicate a greater interest in the discipline, and with it, a greater desire to further delve into
90 psychology (Furnham & Hughes, 2014). However, although there is a decrease in the belief
91 in myths according to academic year these preconceptions do not always disappear
92 completely (Aleksandrova-Howell et al., 2020; Brown, 1983; Gaze, 2014). For example,
93 Gardner and Dalsing (1986) found that a change only occurs when the person has
94 participated in psychology-related courses to the subject of between 19 and 70 hours. In
95 other cases, such as that of Vaughan's study (1977), it was found that university students
96 from different degrees started, on average, defending 40% of a series of misconceptions

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97 about Psychology. Upon completion of an Introductory Psychology Course at university,
98 participants reduced their misconceptions by only 5.5% (Vaughan, 1977). Although none of
99 the studies explicitly state the contents of these introductory courses, which may be a
100 relevant limitation, the results that indicate a relative reduction of these misconceptions
101 seem to be replicated in other studies (McCarthy & Frantz, 2016; Root & Stanley, 2017).
102 This accumulation of evidence on the decline in myth belief is an indication of the benefits,
103 although limited, that formal education seems to grant as the student progresses through the
104 degree (Furnham & Hughes, 2014; Gardner & Dalsing, 1986; Hughes et al., 2015).

105 The type of university can also be a relevant factor to consider. The different types of
106 universities can be differentiated, mainly, through their teaching modality: face-to-face or
107 online (Harmon & Lambrinos, 2006; Zhao et al., 2005). Each teaching modality can attract
108 different types of students. A common practice in the study of myths among the university
109 population has consisted in recruiting students without considering differences according to
110 degree or university in which these higher studies take place (e.g., see Furnham & Bower,
111 1992; Gardner & Brown, 2013; Vaughan, 1977), to maximize external validity. However,
112 there may be more differences than similarities between students from different university
113 backgrounds. For example, the profile of the average student in a face-to-face public
114 university such as the Autonomous University of Madrid (UAM) is usually that of a young
115 adult between the ages of 18 and 24, who is completing their first undergraduate program,
116 without any added family or work responsibilities (Autonomous University of Madrid,
117 2019). In contrast, the profile of the average student from a public online learning
118 university, such as the National Distance Education University (UNED) responds to that of

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119 an adult, with full-time work, greater family responsibilities and previous studies, who
120 seeks to improve their professional skills (García Aretio, 2006). Regarding age,
121 undergraduate students between 23 and 49 years old tend to choose online universities to
122 pursue an undergraduate program (Stewart, Bachman & Johnson, 2010). Such students tend
123 to work more hours weekly than those who choose face-to-face education (Dutton, Dutton
124 & Perry, 2002; Jenkins & Downs, 2003; Mattes, Nanney & Coussans-Read, 2003) and tend
125 to have children and family responsibilities (Conklin, 1997; Dutton, Dutton & Perry 2002;
126 Grimes & Antworth, 1996) In this way, each university could contribute a different student
127 profile and, therefore, could show differences in the belief in misconceptions within
128 Psychology. These variations have not been explored in previous studies and could be
129 relevant in the study of myths in Psychology.

130 Familiarity with scientific dissemination is another factor that may influence the belief in
131 myths. It can be understood as "the use of appropriate skills, media, activities and dialogue
132 to produce one or more of the following personal responses to science: awareness,
133 enjoyment, interest, opinion-forming and understanding" of scientific knowledge (Burns,
134 O'Connor & Stocklmayer, 2003). There are various formats for its use, but not all of them
135 or their contents are equally adequate. While reading academic literature can help reduce
136 belief in myths (Furnham, Callahan & Rawles, 2003), familiarity with content on the
137 Internet can be harmful (e.g., Putnam, 2011). This is due, at least in part, to the absence of
138 supervision mechanisms that guarantee that the informative material on the internet
139 transmits information following the scientific evidence available (Lewandowsky et al.,
140 2012). Also, non-expert psychologists could have difficulties distinguishing scientific vs

141 pseudo-scientific dissemination (see Lilienfeld, Ammirati and David, 2012) which could
142 result not only to not reduce the belief in myths, but increasing it. In addition, scientific
143 dissemination can oversimplify scientific facts to make them more accessible to a non-
144 specialized audience, which can lead to misunderstanding research advances and promoting
145 belief in myths (Lewandowsky et al., 2012; Cassany, López & Martí, 2000). Finally,
146 disseminating false scientific information on social networks can increase its acceptance as
147 correct information simply due to the mere repeated exposure to it, as occurs in other more
148 conventional media (Begg Anas & Farinacci, 1992; Furnham, Callahan & Rawles, 2003).

149 **The methodology used in the evaluation of myth belief**

150 To reduce the prevalence of belief in psychological myths, it is first necessary to adequately
151 detect what these myths are, who believes them and how much they believe in them. This is
152 only possible with valid and reliable evaluation methods. However, many studies in this
153 line of research do not report the psychometric properties of their tools, which may affect
154 the generalization of the results when it comes to reliability and validity (Prieto & Delgado,
155 2010). When studying the prevalence of myths and misconceptions in Psychology, self-
156 report questionnaires have been the default choice as they are a set of tools that allow
157 participants to express both their (dis)agreement and the extent to which they believe that
158 certain statements are true (Bensley & Lilienfeld, 2017; Bensley, Lilienfeld & Powell,
159 2014; Hughes, Lyddy & Lambe, 2013). In this regard, previous literature discusses the
160 relevance of methodological factors such as the response format, content, and psychometric
161 properties of the questionnaires, as well as the characteristics of the samples used in the
162 estimation of myths (Bensley & Lilienfeld, 2017; Hughes, Lyddy & Lambe, 2013; Taylor

163 & Kowalski, 2012). These methodological factors may have influenced how the research
164 was conducted so far, specifically in terms of potential biases (Taylor & Kowalski, 2012).

165 The dichotomous response format (true/false) has been, for many years, the chosen by
166 researchers (Basterfield et al., 2020; Brown, 1983; Ferrero, Garaizar & Vadillo, 2016;
167 Furnham, Callahan & Rawles, 2003; Gardner & Dalsing, 1986; Hughes, Lyddy & Lambe,
168 2013; Kowalski & Taylor, 2004; Lamal, 1995; Taylor & Kowalski, 2004, 2012; Torres,
169 Boccacini & Miller, 2006; Vaughan, 1977). This format is associated with a series of
170 limitations (Bensley & Lilienfeld, 2017; Griggs & Ransdell, 1987; Hughes, Lyddy &
171 Lambe, 2013). One of them is the acquiescence bias, where participants always respond
172 with an affirmative answer (Bensley & Lilienfeld, 2017), thus recommending that the
173 formulation of the statements should be divided into direct and inverse items to prevent
174 response patterns (Taylor & Kowalski, 2004; Griggs & Ransdell, 1987). If all items
175 represent myths and are worded in such a way that the correct answer is “true”, the direct
176 consequence is the overestimation of misconceptions in students as a methodological
177 artifact (Bensley & Lilienfeld, 2015; Griggs & Ransdell, 1987; Taylor & Kowalski, 2012).

178 However, not all studies have carried out this reversal process on items’ wording (e.g., see
179 Gardner & Dalsing, 1986; Vaughan, 1977). When the presentation of the items is balanced
180 (i.e., it is established that approximately half of the items are direct and the other, inverse),
181 the resulting prevalence of believing in myths is lower (Brown, 1983).

182 Another limitation of the T/F format is the impossibility of distinguishing between those
183 responses that represent believing in myths and those that are the product of randomly
184 answering one of the two possible responses (Taylor & Kowalski, 2004). One way to

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185 control this shortcoming has been to add “I don't know” as a third response option
186 (Furnham, 2018; Furnham, Callahan & Rawles, 2003; Gardner & Brown, 2013; Gardner &
187 Dalsing, 1986; Hughes, Lyddy & Lambe, 2013; Lamal, 1995). Although this can add some
188 bias when evaluating those who are not motivated to answer, its introduction makes it
189 possible to discriminate what the students do not know from what they assume as facts and
190 obtain an answer instead of, perhaps, not answering the item - blank (Furnham & Hughes,
191 2014; Furnham, Callahan & Rawles, 2003). The introduction of ‘I don’t know’ response
192 option comprises around 12-13% of the responses (Gardner & Brown, 2013; Gardner &
193 Dalsing, 1986) and reduces the estimate of the prevalence of myths by 8%, which generates
194 a closer and more realistic view of the phenomenon (Gardner & Dalsing, 1986). However,
195 there are still limitations to be solved (Hughes, Lyddy & Lambe, 2013).

196 As an alternative to dichotomous T/F scales, the use of Likert-type scales is proposed in
197 this type of research (Gardner & Brown, 2013; Gardner & Dalsing, 1986; Furnham &
198 Hughes, 2014). By representing different levels of response, it is possible to discriminate
199 with greater certainty the degree of confidence that the participant has in the veracity of the
200 statements. Several authors (Furnham & Hughes, 2014; Gardner & Brown, 2013) use
201 questionnaires with scales that frame a gradient of options from "*completely false*" to
202 "*completely true*", allowing for a greater range of answers and not reducing it to a
203 dichotomous choice. Thus, what is being measured is what the participants believe in a
204 more nuanced way than with the dichotomous response format. One problem with this kind
205 of scale is how participants use the central scores. One way is that they use it to report that
206 they do not know if statemet is true or false. However, also participants could used it to

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207 report that the sentence is half true. In our view, it is important to give participants the
208 option to report that they don't know about the sentence. Because this reason, we labelled
209 the central value of the scale as "don't know". As commented above, that allow a more
210 accurate measure of the participants' beliefs.

211 Others more critical with the methodology have highlighted the content of the
212 questionnaires. The inclusion of myths that are unrepresentative or irrelevant to the
213 discipline, that are not covered by introductory texts, or those that cannot be identified as
214 such, given the available evidence, can bias, in the same way, the estimation of the belief in
215 myths (Bensley & Lilienfeld, 2017; Gardner & Dalsing, 1986; Griggs & Ransdell, 1987;
216 Taylor & Kowalski, 2012).

217 Regarding the samples used, the general sample size in this type of study ranges between
218 100 and 200 participants (eg, see Bensley & Lilienfeld, 2015; Brown, 1983; Furnham &
219 Bower, 1992; Gardner & Brown, 2013; Taylor & Kowalski, 2012; Vaughan, 1977). In
220 studies that involve the use of questionnaires, the use of a sample size of between 200 and
221 400 participants is recommended to carry out an adequate psychometric analysis (Abad et
222 al., 2011). However, their characteristic, so far, has been their low homogeneity in terms of
223 participants' population (Bensley & Lilienfeld, 2015, 2017; Furnham & Hughes, 2014).

224 The participants in this type of research are usually university students from different fields
225 of knowledge who enrol in some Introductory Psychology courses (e.g., see Furnham &
226 Hughes, 2014; Gardner & Brown, 2013; Kowalski & Taylor, 2009). This may favor the
227 generalization of the results to the general population, which is a relevant objective, but
228 makes it difficult to study the evaluation of these ideas among psychology students

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229 throughout their academic career - and it is relevant to know what happens within formal
230 education. A consequence of this could be the variability presented in the systematic
231 reviews carried out so far. Hughes, Lyddy and Lambe (2013) suggest that students who
232 begin Introductory Psychology courses accept between 28% and 71% of these myths. Other
233 studies indicate a recognition that ranges between 30% to 39% of misconceptions (Taylor
234 & Kowalski, 2012).

235 Despite the extensive research on myths in Psychology in other countries -see, for example,
236 Russia (Aleksandrova-Howell et al., 2020), North America (Basterfield et al., 2020;
237 Bensley & Lilienfeld, 2017; Brown, 1983; Gardner & Brown, 2013), United Kingdom
238 (Furnham, Callahan & Rawles, 2003; Furnham & Hughes, 2014; Furnham & Grover,
239 2019), India (Kishore et al., 2011)-, a study of the same characteristics has not yet been
240 carried out in Spain.

241

The present study

242 The present study aims to provide empirical evidence regarding the belief in myths related
243 to Psychology among students enrolled in the Psychology undergraduate program,
244 considering the previously mentioned variables: the academic year, the university in which
245 they are enrolled and the familiarity with scientific dissemination. To do so, an adaptation
246 of one of the available methodological tools with a Likert scale format and with adequate
247 psychometric guarantees is used, in addition to a large sample size to ensure the
248 representativeness of the phenomenon.

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Method

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250 Participants

251 A sample composed of 916 students from the Degree in Psychology from two Spanish
252 universities was used: Autonomous University of Madrid (UAM) (face-to-face, $n = 364$,
253 86% women, aged between 17 and 55 years, $M = 20.03$, $SD = 3.58$) and National Distance
254 Education University (UNED) (online, $n = 552$, 77% women, aged between 18 to 78 years;
255 $M = 35.8$, $SD = 11.6$) (see Table 1 in the supplemental materials to consult the number of
256 participants by year and university).

257 Procedure and Materials

258 Data were collected through participation in the *PsInvestiga* participant recruitment system
259 at the UAM ($n = 238$) and dissemination by institutional email in both universities ($n =$
260 678). All participants completed an online informed consent before the questionnaire.

261 An online questionnaire was sent to participants . This questionnaire measured the
262 demographic data and the belief in Psychology myths. Participants had to fill out the
263 questionnaire individually and their responses were completely anonymous. Before
264 carrying out the task, the student was informed of its purpose and the voluntary nature of
265 their participation. A *demo* of the questionnaire used can be found at this link:
266 <https://forms.gle/6J1EkTT7S9G1iLBH7>. The realization of this project, as well as the
267 treatment of the collected data, has been approved by both the Research Ethics Committee
268 of the Autonomous University of Madrid (code CEI-95-1758) and by the Ethics
269 Subcommittee of the Faculty of Psychology from the same university.

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270 **Demographic measures.** We collected the following data of each participant: age, gender,
271 any other degree previously obtained, the university in which he/she is currently studying
272 Psychology, the highest year of the degree being studied and his/her familiarity with
273 scientific dissemination. Finally, through an open-ended question, participants specified
274 examples of dissemination sources they consult.

275 **Myths in Psychology.** An adaptation of the 55-item questionnaire developed by Gardner
276 and Brown (2013) was carried out. The authors received permission to use this instrument
277 from the copyright holders. Five items were eliminated as they were considered to have
278 little relevance or representativeness for the study and 24 new items were added so that the
279 final questionnaire consisted of 74 items (see Table 2 for items excluded and included in
280 the questionnaire). the 74 items, both those used by Gardner and Brown (2013) and those
281 added by authors, were Psychologyextracted statements taken from the book *50 Great*
282 *Myths of Popular Psychology* (Lilienfeld et al., 2010) accompanied by a five-point Likert-
283 type scale, ranging from 1 (*completely sure it is false*) to 5 (*completely sure it is true*), with
284 3 as the central category (*I don't know*). To control for response bias, some items were
285 reversed: 55.4% of the items (41) were direct and the remaining 44.6% (33) were reversed.
286 Therefore, some items were formulated directly with the statement that is false according to
287 scientific evidence and, in others, the wording indicated the statement was supported by the
288 available evidence. The content of the test sampled different areas of Psychology in a
289 balanced way. When it was presented in Spanish, the standard procedure was followed for
290 its adaptation to the language: translation from English to Spanish by one of the authors,
291 reverse translation by another co-author -from Spanish to English- and a final check carried
292 out by a native expert (independent from the study) to ensure that the two English versions

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293 (the original and the back translation) were equivalent. A psychometric analysis of this tool
294 revealed a Cronbach's alpha indicator of 0.85, which indicates acceptable reliability (Abad
295 et al., 2011).

296

Design and data processing

297 In the present study, a cross-sectional descriptive between-subjects design was used, where
298 the dependent variable was the total score of the "Myths in Psychology" scale. This
299 variable is calculated through the sum of all the scores of each participant's responses with
300 the recoded items (those in which such transformation is required). The higher the scores
301 on the questionnaire, the greater the belief in the myths of this discipline. Three
302 independent variables were taken into account: academic year (with four levels: 1, 2, 3, &
303 4), type of university (with two levels: face-to-face and online) and familiarity with
304 scientific dissemination (with two levels: Yes / No).

305 To explore the effect of the academic year achieved and of the profile of the Psychology
306 student on the belief in myths, a two-factor ANOVA was performed for independent
307 samples (4x2) on the DV "total score" with "year" and "type of university" as factors. On
308 the other hand, a Student's t-test was performed to analyze the effect of the familiarity with
309 scientific dissemination on the prevalence of these beliefs. It was not incorporated into the
310 previous analysis of variance because of the limitations associated with the number of
311 participants who indicated familiarity with scientific dissemination and the impact it has on
312 the assumptions of the statistical model.

313 Following the recommendations on the dissemination of scientific data (e.g., see Björk et
314 al., 2010; Frankenhuis & Nettle, 2018), the database obtained and used in this study is

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315 published on the Open Science Framework platform and is available to any researcher who
316 wishes to consult them at the following link: <https://osf.io/tazg9/>.

317

Results

318 **Descriptives.** The descriptive statistics for the items of the *Myths in Psychology*
319 questionnaire can be found in Table 1, recoded and ordered from highest to lowest score.
320 The graphs of the relative frequencies of items in the total sample can be found in Figures
321 1-4 in the supplemental materials. The mean of the assessment at item-level across the total
322 sample was 2.62 ($SD = 0.16$). If the data were differentiated according to the type of
323 university, in the face-to-face one there was a value of 2.39 ($SD = 0.82$) and, in the online
324 one 2.79 ($SD = 0.15$).

325 As mentioned, each participant could evaluate each item on a 1-5 scale. We identified
326 means around 4 and 5 [>3.5] (*I think it is true* and *Completely sure it is true*) as
327 misconceptions that are accepted by participants. In the other hand, means around 1 and 2
328 [<2.5] (*Completely sure it is false* and *I think it is false*) are considered as detected myths.
329 Therefore, the total sample believed in a total of 9 misconceptions (12.16%); the
330 participants from face-to-face university in 10 (13.51%) and the students of online, in 13
331 (17.56%). Most of the responses revolved around the central score, "I don't know" [2.5-
332 3.5]: for 30 items (40.54%) in the total sample, for 22 (29.73%) in face-to-face and for 38
333 (51.36%) in online. On the other hand, in the total sample, a total of 35 myths (47.3%) were
334 recognized as such; with 42 (56.76%) at face-to-face, and 23 (31.08%) at online (see Table
335 1).

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336 The range of total scores in the questionnaire goes from 74 (score 1 in all myths) to 370
337 (score 5 in all myths). The higher the score, the most belief in myths. For the total sample
338 was obtained a mean score of 194.82 points ($SD = 25.11$, $min. = 128$, $max. = 275$) (Figure
339 1). If the information was analyzed according to the type of university, online presented a
340 higher score ($M = 206.391$, $SD = 22.15$, $min. = 138$, $max. = 275$), in relation to that
341 obtained in face-to-face ($M = 177.274$, $SD = 18.25$, $min. = 128$, $max. = 240$). Higher scores
342 were found among first year students ($M = 202.16$; $SD = 24.84$) compared to those in the
343 final year of the Degree ($M = 181.55$; $SD = 20.95$) (see Table 3 in the supplemental
344 materials to consult the means of the total score, according to university and the academic
345 year).

346 **Effects of type of university and academic year on belief in myths in Psychology.**

347 There was a statistically significant main effect of the type of university factor associated
348 with a large effect size, following Cohen's criteria (1988), $F(1,908) = 65.908$, $p < 0.01$, $\eta_G^2 =$
349 0.216 . This effect shows that face-to-face students believe to a lesser extent in this kind of
350 myths, as the mean total score of this university was lower ($M = 177.27$) than that found
351 among the online students ($M = 206.39$).

352 Although with small effect size, a statistically significant effect was found for the academic
353 year variable, which indicates that beliefs differ according to the year in which the
354 participants are enrolled $F(3,908) = 27.256$, $p < 0.01$, $\eta_G^2 = 0.083$. Multiple *post hoc*
355 comparisons with the Bonferroni correction indicated significant differences between the

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356 first and the rest of the academic years ($p < 0.01$), as well as between the second and the
357 first year and between the second and the fourth year ($p < 0.01$) (see Figure 2).

358 There was a statistically significant effect of the interaction between these two variables.
359 The influence of the academic year on belief in myths was different for students from the
360 two universities participating in the sample, participants from the face-to-face university
361 were less prone than online one to believe in myths, while the latter benefited more from
362 formal education. Although the effect size found was small ($F(3,908) = 8.944$, $p < 0.01$, η_G^2
363 = 0.029) (Figure 2). The summary of the ANOVA results can be found in Table 4 in the
364 supplemental materials.

365 **Effect of familiarity with scientific dissemination**

366 A total of 23.62% ($n = 86$) of the face-to-face university participants claimed familiarity
367 with scientific dissemination. At the online, this figure rose to 27.17% ($n = 150$). In total,
368 236 participants (25.76%) reported performing this activity (see Table 5 in the
369 supplemental materials for a scientific dissemination sources classification).

370 The performance of a Student's *t-test* for independent samples with an associated statistic
371 $t_{425,05} = 3,301$ ($p < 0.001$; $IC95\% = [2.470, 9.742]$) indicates that there was a statistically
372 significant effect of familiarity with scientific dissemination compared to non-familiarity
373 with the belief in myths of Psychology. This effect favors those who claim to do so, by
374 obtaining a lower mean in the total score (Figure 3 and Table 6 in the supplemental
375 materials). However, the effect size found was small (Cohen's $d = 0.244$).

376

Discussion

377 The present study aimed to analyze the prevalence of psychology-related myths in
378 Psychology students in Spain and the influence of three variables on this prevalence: the
379 academic year they are enrolled in, the university in which they study (associated with
380 different characteristic student profiles) and their familiarity with scientific dissemination.
381 The data analyzed sustained that, within the sample used, the variables of academic year,
382 type of university and familiarity with scientific dissemination had a statistically significant
383 effect on the belief in myths in Psychology. The chosen sample size favored the external
384 validity of the study and the generalization of its results to similar populations. According
385 to the data we obtained, it could be concluded that students were capable of recognizing
386 most of the myths that appeared in the questionnaire as such, while they still lacked certain
387 limited knowledge regarding certain aspects of the discipline. Thereby, belief in
388 misconceptions regarding Psychology in the chosen sample cannot be considered high,
389 compared to the values indicated in Hughes, Lyddy and Lambe's review (2013) or
390 compared to the original study by Gardner and Brown (2013).

391 The effects found concerning to the academic year within the Degree in Psychology and the
392 familiarity with scientific dissemination were statistically significant. However, the
393 reported effect sizes were small. This refers to a limitation of the benefits of the different
394 educational tools (formal, as is the case of the degree; informal, in the case of scientific
395 dissemination), which is consistent with the previous literature (e.g., see Furnham &
396 Hughes, 2014; Hughes, Lyddy & Lambe, 2013). Likewise, the trend that was already
397 reflected in the scientific literature was noted - that as the academic year progressed, the
398 proportion of myths decreased (e.g., Gardner & Dalsing, 1986).

20

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399 The effect of the type of university was also statistically significant, with an associated
400 effect size larger than that of the other two factors. Similarly, the academic year had a
401 differential effect on the belief in these myths depending on the university where the
402 psychology studies were carried out. Thus, the reduction in the prevalence of myths that
403 was perceived through the academic year was more prominent at online university. Perhaps
404 it is because these students started from a much higher level of misconceptions. This may
405 be due to the different demographic characteristics that separate these students into
406 different groups as, for example, age. While the face-to-face university, UAM, sample was
407 composed of young people studying their first university degree, the online, UNED, sample
408 showed a mean age difference of one decade. Also, participants from online use to have
409 qualitatively higher familiar and working responsibilities compared to face-to-face
410 participants. City or country of residence could also affect to these results, whereas face-to-
411 face students are living in Madrid or near cities, the online ones are spread all over the
412 world. However, we are aware that our data by themselves cannot explain these differences
413 and more research must be conducted to study them and to find out their causes.

414 Previous studies suggest that, in general, the higher the level of studies, the less belief in
415 myths (Furnham & Hughes, 2014; Gardner & Dalsing, 1986). With these data, it could be
416 postulated that online students should believe less in myths. However, these studies have
417 been carried out in comparison with the general population, and not within the Psychology
418 student body itself. Having accumulated prior knowledge of different areas or the priority
419 that the studies they are studying have in their day to day can be examples of other

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420 variables that are influencing the belief of myths, ensuring a higher score on this type of
421 scales.

422 It is necessary to emphasize that the effect of formal education that we found is quite
423 limited. Possible explanations for this phenomenon would lie in the analysis of what
424 happens in the classroom. The refutational techniques on popularized ideas about
425 Psychology have proven to be effective in this case; however, they are underused or absent
426 (Bensley & Lilienfeld, 2015; Gardner & Dalsing, 1986). The illustration that is made in
427 some subjects of Psychology as a set of isolated plots of knowledge, without any relation to
428 each other, can also be counterproductive. This is consistent with what some studies
429 pointed out: after discussing misconceptions in class, belief in them decreases, but re-
430 emerges when moving to a different topic (Lyddy & Hughes, 2012). It is the so-called
431 *rebound effect* (Lewandowsky et al., 2012). That is, the explanations that are given do not
432 acquire the degree of generalization necessary for them to produce stable modifications
433 over time in the beliefs of the students. In addition, it is possible that belief in myths could
434 be enhanced within the universities. Some authors indicate that problems when teaching
435 introductory courses on the philosophy of science that supports Psychology can influence
436 the subsequent development of misconceptions in this regard (García García et al., 2006).
437 By not knowing the scope, implications, and characteristics of this discipline, it is difficult
438 to distinguish between what is valid and what is not.

439 In this study, familiarity with scientific dissemination proved to have a positive but limited
440 effect. Only a small proportion of the sample claimed to carry out such activity and it was
441 more frequent among the online participants. Two characteristics shared by some sources

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442 of dissemination considered is that they are accessible and practical, which favors their
443 propensity. The journals that have the title "Psychology" and other complementary words,
444 widely disseminated without their recognition being due to the scientific quality of their
445 contents, may present partial truths or biased statements that, although well directed, are not
446 completely correct. As they are not reviewed by accredited specialists in the field, there is
447 no possible filter. Part of the reduced effect size found could be explained by this. As
448 reported in Lewandowsky et al. (2012), the fact that now people stopped having a passive
449 role and have begun to create content in the media (often online) can spread
450 misinformation, rather than having an exclusively positive side. Also, social media allow
451 the possibility of creating a community between users with the same interests is added.
452 While the debates that take place online can be enriching, the effect that can be obtained is
453 the opposite when handling information that is not verified. Some studies have already
454 explored the possible advantages of using social networks such as Twitter in the academic
455 world (e.g., see Letierce et al., 2010). Students must be provided with the appropriate tools
456 that will allow them to make the most of these information options.

457 The present study has also some limitations to consider. Firstly, the item presentation order
458 was predefined by experimenters and the same for all participants. This could cause some
459 undesirable effects such as fatigue or practice effects, that affect to participants' responses.
460 Future studies may consider to randomize or counterbalance the order of item presentation
461 to avoid these effects and their influence on the measure of the believe in myths. Also,
462 future studies could measure, not only the belief in myths, but also the participants'

23

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463 knowledge of true ideas about human behavior. That will allow researchers to compare
464 these two approaches and explore if there is a relation between them.

465 Another limitation of our study is related with the measure of the scientific dissemination
466 variable, what could negatively affect our results and make them less precises. While the
467 university and the academic year are easy to answer questions, measuring the familiarity
468 with scientific dissemination is less so. For example, participants may don't know what
469 scientific dissemination is or have an incorrect idea of it. Also, participants could be not
470 able to distinguish scientific vs pseudo-scientific dissemination, which not only will
471 decrease the belief in myths but could it makes increase. Finally, we did not distinguish
472 how much participants are familiar with scientific dissemination. Although our results
473 pointed out that those participants that reported scientific dissemination believing less in
474 myths than those that do not in both universities, to assess this factor more precisely and to
475 delve deeper into how these two variables -being familiar with scientific dissemination and
476 how much so- are related, probably using more than one question to do so, to obtain a more
477 sensible measure.

478 As far we know, the authors of the original test we used did not analyze its construct and
479 convergent validity, neither we do. In order to provide more reliable information, this could
480 be analyzed and reported. Finally, it is recommendable to estimate the sample size needed
481 to achieve adequate statistical power. Here we did not estimate it, but we tried to obtain the
482 most participants as possible. Future research could calculate the minimun necessary
483 sample size following the recommendations for this kind of research (e.g., Hair et al. 2010).

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Conclusions

486 The results of the present study offer a sample of the belief in myths in Psychology among
487 students of this discipline in Spain. Thus, there is no clear defense of myths as true
488 statements by psychology students, although a large number of responses were found to be
489 around the mean value of the scale ("*I don't know*"). The main conclusions of the study
490 could be summarized in these three: a) Students enrolled in higher academic years tend to
491 believe less in myths than those who coursing initial years; b) Familiarity with scientific
492 dissemination is paired to a decrement in the belief in myths, although its benefits seem
493 restricted in scope; c) Prevalence of belief in myths varies according to the characteristics
494 of the universities of origin, in such a way that students enrolled in a online university
495 belief more than those who belong to a face-to-face one. Another interesting finding is that
496 participants of online university experience a greater reduction in belief in this type of
497 misconceptions through year, but they do not reach the level from which students enrolled
498 in face-to-face universities start.

499 It is known that accepting myths in psychology as true correlates with accepting other
500 misconceptions in other fields, such as the belief in paranormal events or in
501 pseudoscientific practices as true practices (Bensley, Lilienfeld & Powell, 2014). Given that
502 this type of study is beginning to be carried out in Spain, future lines of research should
503 explore other possible variables, beyond those analyzed in this study, for their connection
504 with the belief in these types of ideas. Identifying the myths currently held by students is
505 the first step in establishing effective interventions. Treating these misconceptions early is
506 necessary to train professionals who, on the applied side, provide the most effective

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507 services for their users and that, on the theoretical side, do not compromise the

508 advancement of behavioral science with these obstacles.

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509

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511

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FIGURES CAPTION

730 Figure 1. Histogram of the total score obtained in the questionnaire.

731 Figure 2. Effect of the interaction between university and academic year on the total score
732 of the questionnaire.

733 Figure 3. Effect of the familiarity with scientific dissemination on the total score (by type of
734 university).

Table 1 (on next page)

Table 1

Means and standard deviations (in parentheses) of the questionnaire items as a function of the total and separated by university. Ordered from highest to lowest by the score obtained in the total sample. Inverse test items are included, recoded, so that a higher mean indicates greater belief in the misconception.

Table 1.

Means and standard deviations (in parentheses) of the questionnaire items as a function of the total and separated by university. Ordered from highest to lowest by the score obtained in the total sample. Inverse test items are included, recoded, so that a higher mean indicates greater belief in the misconception.

ITEM	Tot	Face	Onli
	al	-to-	ne
	Me	Mea	Mea
	an	n	n
	(SD	(SD)	(SD)
)))
13. Individuals commonly DON'T repress the memories of traumatic experiences. (*)	4.27 (1.04)	4.03 (1.14)	4.44 (0.94)
25. Students learn best when teaching styles are matched to their learning styles.	4.22 (0.9)	4.10 (0.88)	4.30 (0.90)
12. When dying, people DON'T pass through a universal series of psychological stages. (*)	4.12 (1.07)	3.83 (1.13)	4.32 (0.98)
5. Subliminal messages can't persuade people to perform some behaviors. (*)	4.1 (1.2)	3.95 (1.23)	4.29 (1.16)
17. Some people have true photographic memories.	4.07 (1.02)	3.75 (1.12)	4.29 (0.89)
58. Most people who experience severe trauma, (e.g., as in military combat) DON'T	3.96	3.80 (1.11)	4.07 (1.04)

develop posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD). (*)	(1.07)))
68. More experienced therapists are generally NO more effective than those with little experience. (*)	3.77 (1.09)	3.76 (1.06)	3.77 (1.11)
28. Hypnotized people are aware of their surroundings and can recall the details of conversations overheard during hypnosis. (*)	3.72 (1.12)	3.32 (1.15)	2.90 (1.07)
72. Electroconvulsive therapy is rarely administered today.	3.67 (1.10)	3.7 (1.09)	3.66 (1.12)
26. Direct instruction is superior to discovery learning. (*)	3.49 (1.2)	3.41 (1.14)	3.54 (1.24)
46. People's attitudes are NOT highly predictive of their behaviors. (*)	3.48 (1.21)	3.25 (1.26)	3.62 (1.16)
21. There is a modest correlation between brain size and IQ in humans. (*)	3.44 (1.24)	3.55 (1.31)	3.36 (1.18)
67. Crowding consistently leads to more aggression.	3.43 (1.08)	3.61 (1.03)	3.30 (1.10)
38. Positive thinking is better than negative thinking for all people.	3.38 (1.31)	2.95 (1.28)	3.67 (1.25)
15. The memory of everything we've experienced is stored permanently in our brains, even if we can't access all of it.	3.36 (1.3)	2.91 (1.42)	3.66 (1.30)

	9)		
	3.3	3.08	3.47
64. Most people that plead insanity are NOT faking mental illness. (*)	2 (1.0 4)	(0.95)	(1.07)
	3.2	3.16	3.37
33. Awakening a sleepwalker is NOT dangerous. (*)	9 (1.4)	(1.42)	(1.36)
	3.2	3.22	3.18
7. People become increasingly satisfied with their lives in old age. (*)	0 (1.0 9)	(1.08)	(1.10)
	3.2	2.88	3.42
50. Most children survive the divorce of their parents without much, if any, long-term psychological damage. (*)	0 (1.2 2)	(1.23)	(1.17)
	3.1	3.08	3.20
35. Ulcers are caused primarily by stress.	5 (1.1)	(1.04)	(1.13)
	3.1	2.53	3.52
39. Voice stress analyzers can help to detect lying.	3 (1.2 3)	(1.21)	(1.08)
	2.9	3.02	2.95
23. Irregularly provided feedback best promotes long-term learning. (*)	8 (1.2 5)	(1.27)	(1.25)
	2.9	2.54	3.19
60. Hallucinations are almost always a sign of serious mental illness.	3 (1.2 9)	(1.20)	(1.28)
	2.9	2.57	3.13
31. Our brains rest during sleep.	1 (1.5	(1.41)	(1.52)

)		
	2.9	2.4	3.26
36. Women are NO better than men at accurately guessing the feelings of others. (*)	1 (1.3 4)	(1.28)	(1.28)
	2.8	2.38	3.22
4. Extrasensory perception is NOT a real phenomenon. (*)	8 (1.4 2)	(1.43)	(1.32)
	2.8	3.08	2.66
44. The best way to change someone's attitude is to give them a large reward to do so.	3 (1.3 1)	(1.34)	(1.27)
	2.8	3.03	2.67
42. Expressing anger directly toward another person or object makes us more aggressive. (*)	1 (1.1 7)	(1.07)	(1.20)
	2.8	2.99	2.71
8. Most adopted children are psychologically healthy.	(0.9 9)	(1.02)	(0.96)
	2.8	2.53	2.98
49. Most people who were physically abused as children DON'T go on to become abusers themselves. (*)	(1.2 1)	(1.22)	(1.18)
	2.7	2.62	2.89
57. All clinically depressed people suffer from extreme sadness.	8 (1.3 2)	(1.30)	(1.33)
	2.7	3.04	2.59
20. IQ scores are relatively unstable during childhood. (*)	7 (1.0 8)	(1.10)	(1.03)
	2.7	2.72	2.74
61. Homicide is more common than suicide.	3 (1.2 4)	(1.22)	(1.26)
22. As a general rule. students typically recall	2.7	2.35	2.95

only 10% of what they read.	1 (1.1)	(1.04)	(1.07)
71. Taking a placebo (i.e. sugar pill) can change brain functioning and its chemistry. (*)	2.6 8 (1.3 8)	2.66 (1.39)	2.70 (1.37)
24. Negative reinforcement is a type of punishment.	2.6 5 (1.6 1)	1.88 (1.37)	3.16 (1.55)
55. People with schizophrenia DON'T have multiple personalities. (*)	2.6 5 (1.3)	2.31 (1.23)	2.88 (1.30)
11. Playing classic music to infants DON'T boosts their intelligence. (*)	2.6 3 (1.4)	1.82 (1.19)	3.16 (1.27)
29. It is impossible to lie under hypnosis.	2.5 2 (1.0 1)	2.34 (1.03)	2.64 (0.98)
27. Hearing material while we are asleep (sleep learning) can be an effective aid to learning.	2.4 2 (1.2 5)	1.8 (1.07)	2.84 (1.20)
63. The words "insanity" and "sanity" are purely legal NOT psychological terms. (*)	2.4 (1.1 6)	2.23 (1.08)	2.52 (1.19)
73. Expert judgment and intuition are the best means of making clinical decisions.	2.3 9 (1.2 2)	2.11 (1.16)	2.58 (1.24)
37. Unfamiliarity breeds contempt: We dislike things we have less exposure to. (*)	2.3 7	2.19 (1.09	2.50 (1.13

	(1.1 2)))
45. Men and women communicate in completely different ways.	2.3 (1.1 8)	1.81 (0.98)	2.61 (1.19)
53. People's responses to inkblots tell us a great deal about their personalities.	2.2 9 (1.2 9)	1.52 (0.97)	2.80 (1.22)
43. Groups tend to make less extreme decisions than individuals.	2.2 8 (1.4)	1.94 (1.23)	2.52 (1.45)
9. Married couples enjoy more marital satisfaction after they have children.	2.2 3 (0.9 4)	2.29 (0.95)	2.18 (0.94)
18. Human memory works like a tape recorder, and accurate records events we've experienced.	2.1 6 (1.2 3)	1.54 (0.94)	2.57 (1.33)
40. We are most romantically attracted to people who are similar to us. (*)	2.1 5 (1.1 5)	1.93 (1.11)	2.30 (1.15)
74. Most modern therapies are NOT based on the teachings of Freud. (*)	2.1 4 (1.1 4)	1.92 (1.06)	2.29 (1.17)
59. Psychiatric hospital admissions and crimes DON'T increase during full moons. (*)	2.1 2 (1.3 9)	1.46 (1.07)	2.56 (1.41)
56. There has recently been a massive epidemic of childhood autism.	2.0 8 (1.1	2.03 (1.09	2.11 (1.12)

	0)		
	2.0	1.24	2.62
1. Most people use only about 10% of their brain power.	7 (1.3	(0.76	(1.43
	8)))
	2.0	1.44	2.44
6. Humans have an invisible body energy that can cause psychological problems when blocked.	4 (1.2	(0.75	(1.36
	5)))
	1.9	1.96	2.02
62. Most rapes are committed by strangers.	9 (1.0	(1.04	(1.02
	2)))
	1.9	1.86	2.05
19. Rote memorization is NOT the best way to retain information. (*)	7 (1.1	(1.05	(1.18
	3)))
	1.9	1.36	2.35
34. The polygraph (lie detector) test is NOT an accurate means of detecting dishonesty. (*)	6 (1.1	(0.81	(1.19
	6)))
	1.9	1.87	2.02
66. Rehabilitation programs have NO effect on the recidivism rates of criminals.	6 (0.9	(0.87	(1.02
	6)))
	1.9	1.84	2.03
41. The more people present at an emergency, the greater the chance that someone will intervene.	5 (1.3	(1.35	(1.32
	4)))
	1.8	1.78	1.95
14. People with amnesia can still recall some details of their earlier lives. (*)	8 (0.9	(0.93	(1.00
	7)))
	1.8	1.46	2.13
16. With effort, we can remember events back to the time of our birth.	6 (1.0	(0.72	(1.16
	6)))

	5)		
	1.8		
2. Almost all color-blind people can see at least some colors. (*)	4 (1.0 6)	1.85 (1.02 6)	1.84 (1.08)
47. We CANNOT tell a person's personality by merely looking at their handwriting. (*)	4 (1.1 9)	1.23 (0.72)	2.24 (1.26)
52. The fact that a trait is heritable means we CAN'T change it.	3 (1.1)	1.64 (1.02)	1.96 (1.14)
69. Most psychotherapy involves a couch and exploring one's early past.	5) (1.1	1.66 (1.11	1.89 (1.17)
51. Obese people are more cheerful ("jolly") than thin people.	2) 1.7 1 (0.9 2)	1.6 (0.82)	1.87 (0.96)
65. Most psychopaths are violent.	8 (0.8 8)	1.52 (0.77)	1.80 (0.93)
3. Some people are exclusively left-brained while others are right-brained.	1) 1.6 7 (1.0 1)	1.27 (0.55)	1.94 (1.16)
54. Only deeply depressed people commit suicide.	7) 1.6 4 (0.9 7)	1.47 (0.9)	1.75 (1.00)
70. Antidepressants are much more effective than psychotherapy for treating depression.	5) 1.6 3 (0.8 5)	1.54 (0.81)	1.70 (0.87)

	1.6	1.64	1.58
30. Virtually all people dream. (*)	(0.96)	(0.93)	(0.98)
10. Infants establish attachment bonds only to their mothers.	1.45 (0.87)	1.12 (0.44)	1.66 (1.01)
48. Knowing a person's astrological sign predicts their personality traits at better than chance levels.	1.42 (0.84)	1.18 (0.61)	1.59 (0.94)
32. Researchers have demonstrated that dreams possess symbolic meaning.	1.36 (1.3)	1.77 (1.09)	2.75 (1.29)

Note: In bold are those items that exceed the "myth" threshold established by the researchers (Mean > 3.5). In italics, those items included in the "I don't know" category ($2.5 \geq \text{Mean} \geq 3.5$).

Figure 1

Figure 1. Histogram of the total score obtained in the questionnaire.

Figure 2

Figure 2

Effect of the interaction between university and academic year on the total score of the questionnaire.

Figure 3

Effect of the familiarity with scientific dissemination on the total score (by university).

